

#	Suggested sequence	Learning type	Day	Date and time	Moderators	Trainer(s)	Topic	Link	Status
1	Live		Tuesday	2025-11-04 09:00 - 12:00	Value withheld to maintain c	Value withheld to maintain confidentiality.	Foundations of RDM for beginners	https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006452660	Confirmed
2	Self-learning				None	None	Foundations of RDM for trainers	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4071470	Confirmed
3	Live		Thursday	2025-11-06 09:00 - 12:00	Value withheld to maintain c	Value withheld to maintain confidentiality.	Practical Data Protection in Research		Confirmed
4	Self-learning				None	None	Open Science	https://book.the-turing-way.org/reproducible-resear	Confirmed
5	Live		Tuesday	2025-11-11 09:00 - 12:00	Value withheld to maintain c	Value withheld to maintain confidentiality.	Python for beginners	https://swcarpentry.github.io/python-novice-inflam	Pending
6	Self-learning				None	None	Python for advanced	https://carpentries-incubator.github.io/python-inter	Confirmed
7	Live		Thursday	2025-11-13 09:00 - 12:00	Value withheld to maintain c	Value withheld to maintain confidentiality.	Git for beginners and advanced in parallel	https://swcarpentry.github.io/git-novice/ , https://ca	Pending
8	Self-learning				None	None	Git for beginners	https://book.the-turing-way.org/reproducible-resear	Confirmed
9	Live		Tuesday	2025-11-18 09:00 - 12:00	Value withheld to maintain c	Value withheld to maintain confidentiality.	Introduction to Galaxy	https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/	Confirmed
10	Self-learning				None	None	Train-the-trainer workshop on DMPs	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771035	Confirmed
11	Live		Thursday	2025-11-21 09:00 - 12:00	Value withheld to maintain c	Value withheld to maintain confidentiality.	Didactics & Motivation	https://carpentries.github.io/instructor-training/	Pending
12	Self-learning				None	None	Sharing Data & Metadata	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16792999	Confirmed